

Toxic marine microalgae and associated phycotoxins in shellfish: 14 years of data from the Italian coasts

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Abstract

Along the Italian coasts, toxins of algal origin in wild and cultivated shellfish have been reported since the 1970s. In this study, we used data gathered by the Veterinary Public Health Institutes and the Italian Environmental Health Protection Agencies from 2006 to 2019 to investigate toxicity events and relate them to the distribution of toxic species. Among detected toxins (OA and analogs, YTXs, PTXs, STXs, DAs, AZAs), OA and YTX were those most frequently reported in cases of seafood contamination. Levels of those toxins exceeding regulatory limits for OA were associated with high abundances of *Dinophysis* spp. and for YTX with blooms of *Gonyaulax spinifera*, *Lingulodinium polyedra*, and *Protoceratium reticulatum*. Seasonal blooms of *Pseudo-nitzschia* spp. occurred all along the Italian coast, but DA was only occasionally found in shellfish, at concentrations consistently below the regulatory limit. *Alexandrium* was recorded in many more areas than STXs, which only rarely exceeded the regulatory limit. *Azadinium* was sporadically recorded, and AZAs were sometimes detected in low quantities. Among the emerging toxins, PLTX-like toxins often accumulated in wild mussels and sea urchins due to the occurrences of *Ostreopsis* cf. *ovata*. Overall, Italian coastal waters harbour numerous potentially toxic species, with a few HAB hotspots related to DSP toxins. Still, rare cases of intoxications have occurred so far, reflecting the whole Mediterranean Sea conditions.

Keywords: domoic acid, emerging toxins, marine lipophilic toxins, paralytic shellfish toxins, toxic algae

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Introduction

The European legislation limits the commercialization of seafood for human consumption when contaminated by phycotoxins, setting a threshold level for each toxin (European Council, 2004) processing and distribution of food and to exports, and without any prejudice to more specific requirements relating to food hygiene. The following principles are taken into special account: The recent finding of toxins never detected before in European coasts led the European Food Safety Authority (EFSA) to express a series of scientific opinions concerning these emerging biotoxins, for which regulatory limits are not established yet.

Observations of HABs in Italy date from the 1970s (Pistocchi *et al.*, 2012) which is highly exploited for mollusk farming, the first occurrence of human intoxication due to shellfish consumption occurred in 1989, nearly 10 years later than other countries in Europe and worldwide that had faced similar problems. Until 1997, Adriatic mollusks had been found to be contaminated mostly by diarrhetic shellfish poisoning toxins (i.e., okadaic acid and dinophysistoxins. However, it was not until 1989 that the first shellfish contamination by okadaic acid (OA) was reported in the northern Adriatic Sea, in concomitance with the presence of *Dinophysis fortii* in the water column (Fattorusso *et al.*, 1992). Since then, toxic outbreaks due to harmful algal blooms (HABs) have also been observed in the Tyrrhenian and Ionian Seas, encompassing the entire Italian coastline.

In this study, we analyzed the data gathered from 2006 to 2019 by the Italian Veterinary

Public Health Institutes and the Environmental Health Protection Agencies, which are the authorities responsible for the monitoring of biotoxins in cultivated and wild seafood and of toxic phytoplankton. Our aim was to investigate toxicity events along the Italian coasts and relate them to the distribution of potentially toxic species.

Material and Methods

Shellfish samples (mainly mussel *Mytilus galloprovincialis*) were collected from 2006 to 2019 in fortnightly frequency from aquaculture farms located along the coasts of Abruzzo, Apulia, Campania, Emilia-Romagna, Friuli-Venezia Giulia, Lazio, Liguria, Marche, Molise, Sardinia, Sicily, Tuscany, and Veneto regions. For toxin analysis, shellfish were opened, deprived of the shell, and washed with running water to remove any residues. Then, each sample was homogenized with a blender and stored at $-20\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ until the analysis. The lipophilic toxins (Okadaic Acid (OA) and analogs, Pectenotoxins (PTXs), Yessotoxins (YTXs), Azaspiracids (AZAs)), Saxitoxins (STXs) and Domoic Acid (DA) were analyzed at the Veterinary Public Health Institutes following the methods provided for by the European legislation (Commission Regulation (EC) 2074/2005).

Shellfish samples were considered positive when contaminated by phycotoxin levels above the thresholds indicated by the European Council (EC) Regulation No. 853/2004 and subsequent amendments: $160\text{ }\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$ for OA and analogs, PTXs, and AZAs, 20 mg kg^{-1} for DA, 0.8 mg kg^{-1} for STXs, and 3.75 mg kg^{-1} for YTXs.

Seawater samples for phytoplankton analysis were collected in the same areas with both 20 μm mesh nets and bottles following the Intergovernmental Oceanographic Commission guide (Reguera *et al.*, 2016). Samples were preserved by adding acid or neutral Lugol solution. Toxic or potentially toxic species were counted following the Utermöhl method (European Standard, 2006).

Results and Discussion

Shellfish collected along the Italian coastal waters were found to accumulate most of the major known algal toxins. Okadaic acid and analogs, YTXs, PTXs, STXs, DAs, AZAs, were recorded in shellfish tissues in several regions over the sampling period (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Microalgal toxins (AZA = Azaspiracid; DA = Domoic Acid; OAs = Okadaic Acid and analogs, PTX = Pectenotoxin, STX = Saxitoxins, YTX = Yessotoxin) in shellfish tissues along the Italian coasts (2006-2019). Red and yellow: toxin concentrations at least once above and below the EU limits, respectively. Green: no toxins recorded. Grey: data not available.

Okadaic acid and analogs and YTXs were the most frequently reported toxins in

seafood in Italy, as also reported for the rest of the Mediterranean Sea (Zingone *et al.*, 2020)HABs. Their concentrations were often above the legal limits and caused the closure of shellfish farms as well as a few cases of DSP diagnoses in humans (Lugliè *et al.*, 2011; Pistocchi *et al.*, 2012) which is highly exploited for mollusk farming, the first occurrence of human intoxication due to shellfish consumption occurred in 1989, nearly 10 years later than other countries in Europe and worldwide that had faced similar problems. Until 1997, Adriatic mollusks had been found to be contaminated mostly by diarrhetic shellfish poisoning toxins (i.e., okadaic acid and dinophysistoxins. Azaspiracids and DAs never exceeded the EU limits, while STXs values above the EU limit were found in Sardinia and Sicily.

Several potentially toxic species were recorded during the study period (Table 1). A relationship between potentially toxic algae abundances and toxin levels in seafood was only found in some regions and was related to the presence of OA and YTX.

Dinophysis (mainly *D. acuminata* complex, *D. caudata*, *D. tripos* and *D. fortii*) were frequently reported in those regions affected by mussel contamination by OA above the EU limits. Their maximum abundances usually did not exceed 10^2 cells L^{-1} , with some exceptions reaching the maximum of 7,700 cells L^{-1} in 2012 (*D. acuminata* complex), exceeding the previous maximum Mediterranean record of $\sim 2,000$ cells L^{-1} from Slovenian waters (Francé *et al.*, 2018).

Table 1. Potentially toxic species identified in light microscopy along the Italian coasts from 2006 to 2019 and associated types of toxins.

<i>Bacillariophyceae</i>	Toxins
<i>Halamphora coffeiformis</i>	DA
<i>Pseudo-nitzschia australis</i>	DA
<i>Pseudo-nitzschia cf. delicatissima</i>	DA
<i>Pseudo-nitzschia cf. fraudulenta</i>	DA
<i>Pseudo-nitzschia cf. pseudodelicatissima</i>	DA
<i>Pseudo-nitzschia galaxiae</i>	DA
<i>Pseudo-nitzschia multiseriis</i>	DA
<i>Pseudo-nitzschia multistriata</i>	DA
<i>Pseudo-nitzschia pungens</i>	DA
<i>Pseudo-nitzschia subpacificica</i>	DA
<i>Dinophyceae</i>	
<i>Alexandrium minutum</i>	STX
<i>Alexandrium ostenfeldii</i>	STX, CIs
<i>Alexandrium pacificum</i>	STX
<i>Alexandrium pseudogonyaulax</i>	GDA
<i>Alexandrium tamarense</i>	STX
<i>Alexandrium taylorii</i>	STX, GDA
<i>Azadinium dexteroporum</i>	AZA
<i>Azadinium poporum</i>	AZA
<i>Dinophysis acuminata</i>	OA
<i>Dinophysis acuta</i>	OA
<i>Dinophysis caudata</i>	OA
<i>Dinophysis fortii</i>	OA
<i>Dinophysis ovum</i>	OA
<i>Dinophysis sacculus</i>	OA
<i>Dinophysis tripos</i>	OA
<i>Gonyaulax spinifera</i>	YTX
<i>Gymnodinium catenatum</i>	STX
<i>Lingulodinium polyedra</i>	YTX
<i>Ostreopsis cf. ovata</i>	PLTX-like
<i>Phalacroma mitra</i>	OA
<i>Phalacroma rotundatum</i>	OA
<i>Prorocentrum lima</i>	OA, CIs
<i>Prorocentrum rhathymum/mexicanum</i>	OA
<i>Protoceratium reticulatum</i>	YTX

Gonyaulax spinifera, *Protoceratium reticulatum* and *Lingulodinium polyedra* were frequently reported in those regions affected by YTX mussel contamination above the EU limits.

Seasonal blooms of *Pseudo-nitzschia* spp. often attained 10^6 cells L^{-1} , but DA was only occasionally detected and never above regulatory limit (Rossi *et al.*, 2016). The low DA levels in seafood even in bloom conditions could be explained considering that (i) cryptic species (some toxic and some non-toxic) can co-occur, and (ii) toxicity may vary within individual species (Giulietti *et al.*, 2021).

Azadinium spp. were sporadically recorded, while AZAs have been occasionally detected but always under the regulatory limits. This could be explained by the low toxicity of those *Azadinium* species (Giuliani *et al.*, 2019) novel AZAs produced by the Mediterranean dinoflagellate *Azadinium dexteroporum* were discovered (AZA-54, AZA-55, 3-epi-AZA-7, AZA-56, AZA-57 and AZA-58 which, in addition, never reached high abundances throughout the years.

Alexandrium minutum, *A. tamarense* and *A. pacificum* were recorded in many more areas than STXs and exceeded 10^5 cells L^{-1} in Sicily and Sardinia when STXs exceeded the regulatory limit. In other regions, *Alexandrium* species were commonly recorded but with low abundances (generally 10^2 cells L^{-1}), while the co-occurrence of both toxic and non-toxic species (or species producing other toxins, e.g. spirolides for *A. ostenfeldii*, Ciminiello *et al.*, 2006) might explain the lack of limit-exceeding STX levels in seafood samples.

Fig. 2. PLTXs (Palytoxin-like compounds), CIs (Cyclic imines) and TTXs (tetrodotoxins) recorded in seafood along the Italian coast. Red colour indicates toxin concentration above EFSA opinion. Grey: not available.

Among the emerging toxins, one of the most important classes in the Mediterranean Sea are the PLTX-like compounds produced by several *Ostreopsis* species, benthic dinoflagellates whose blooms (up to 10^6 cells g^{-1} of macroalgal fresh weight) have become regular phenomena in summer and autumn along all the Italian coasts in the last decades (Emilia-Romagna and Veneto are the only exceptions). PLTX-like toxins have often accumulated in seafood during *Ostreopsis* cf. *ovata* blooms, often with concentrations exceeding the EFSA threshold (EFSA, 2009).

Cyclic imines (spirolides and gymnodimines, related to *Alexandrium ostenfeldii*) and tetrodotoxins (related to bacteria) were recorded in seafood often with concentrations

exceeding the EFSA threshold (EFSA 2017) (Fig. 2). Recently, also *Prorocentrum cordatum* was related to TTX-like compounds' production when associated to specific bacteria (Rodríguez *et al.*, 2017).

Overall, the Italian coastal waters support numerous potentially toxic species, but the cases of intoxication are relatively rare and impacts on aquaculture are limited to a few hot spots in the northern Adriatic Sea, where DSP is the main concern. A variety of toxins have been detected in several instances in microalgae strains from these waters (Pistocchi *et al.*, 2012), while seafood toxicity, when detected, has commonly remained below the safety limits. Therefore, no clear trends in occurrence nor expansions emerge for either toxic microalgae or seafood contamination in Italian coasts, in line with what has been observed in the rest of Mediterranean Sea (Zingone *et al.*, 2020) HABs.

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